

Deep Kegel and Breathing Exercises: Effect on Personal Characteristics and Body Mass Index of Elderly Women with Urinary Incontinence

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Abstract:

Background: Kegel's exercise instruction should focus on isolation of pelvic muscles, avoidance of buttock, abdomen and thigh muscle contraction. **Aim of the study:** evaluate evaluate effect of deep breathing and kegel exercises on personal characteristics and body mass index among elderly women with urinary incontinence. **Design:** A quasi-experimental study design was utilized in this study (one group pre and post-test). **Sample:** A purposive sample was selected and this study was performed on 100 Menopausal women diagnosed with stress urinary incontinence. **Setting:** gynecological and urological outpatient clinics Beni-Suef university hospital. **Tools:** Data was collected using 1) a structure interviewing questionnaire schedule, 2) The International Consultation on Incontinence Modular Questionnaire 3) Pelvic floor muscles exercises checklist. **Results:** The mean weight of the studied sample was 82.680 ± 11.8815 , mean height was 160.420 ± 2.8610 , and mean of BMI was 32.1224 ± 4.47973 . A highly statistically significant differences in the frequency of urine leakage, decrease in the severity of urinary incontinence, of the studied sample after intervention than pre-intervention, also there were statistical differences in the amount of urine leaked per day were found. **Conclusion:** A negative correlation between age of the studied sample and their adherence to practicing deep breathing and Kegel exercises throughout the study was found. It reveals improvement of frequency of urinary incontinence for overweight and obese women. There was statistically significant association between BMI and frequency of urinary incontinence among the studied sample. Moreover, a negative correlation between deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence and severity of stress urinary incontinence was found. **Recommendations:** Developing awareness program regarding importance and benefits of practicing deep breathing and kegel exercises to reduce stress urinary incontinence symptoms among elderly women.

Keywords: Deep breathing, Elderly women, Kegel exercise, Stress urinary incontinence, personal characteristics, body mass index

Introduction

Elder women refer to women age 50 and older. Ageing women refers to the same chronological group but emphasizes that ageing is a process that occurs at very different rates among various individuals and groups. Privileged women may remain free of the health concerns that often accompany ageing until well into their 70s and 80s. Others who endure a lifetime of poverty, malnutrition and heavy labor may be chronologically young but functionally “old” at age 40. The more traditional Africans definitions of an elderly person correlates with chronological age of 50 to 65 years, depending on the setting, the region and the country [1-5].

Kegel's exercise instruction should focus on isolation of pelvic muscles, avoidance of buttock, abdomen and thigh muscle contraction. Moderate repetitions of the strongest contraction possible (3 sets of 8 to 10 contractions held for 6 to 8 seconds 3 to 4 times a week) and contraction for progressively longer times (up to 10 seconds if possible) [6-8]. Arnold H. Kegel who firstly described the pelvic floor muscle exercise recommended starting the exercises with 5 to 25 repetitions a day as the pelvic floor muscles strengthened. The muscle contraction time should be about 8-10 seconds. Over the years, many different sets of exercises to strengthen the pelvic floor muscles have been proposed.

However, there is no optimal pattern for performing these exercises as regards the correct number of repetitions, strength and duration of muscle contraction [9].

Women with mixed urinary incontinence often experience symptom reduction as they embark on behavioral changes that may include weight loss, timed voiding or bladder retraining and fluid optimization. These interventions can be initiated without exhaustive diagnostic work-up, unless signs or symptoms suggest a need for specialist referral [10].

Aim of the study

To evaluate effect of deep breathing and kegel exercises on personal characteristics and body mass index among elderly women with urinary incontinence through:

1. Evaluate urinary incontinence according to ICIQ-SF scale before and after practice of deep breathing and Kegel exercise.
2. Assess correlation between deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence and personal characteristics of the elderly women through the program phases.
3. Assess correlation between body mass index and frequency of micturition through the intervention phases

Hypothesis

1. Remarkable improvement in urinary incontinence according to ICIQ-SF scale will be observed after practice of deep breathing and Kegel exercise.
2. Deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence will be affected by personal characteristics of the elderly women.
3. The severity of incontinence adheres to deep breathing and kegel exercises for the elderly women through the intervention phases

Subject and methods

Study design: A quasi-experimental one group (pre-post) test study design.

Study Setting: Gynecological and urological outpatient clinics at Beni-Suef University Hospital.

Sampling: A Purposive sample (100 women) was used from the above-mentioned setting.

Tools of data collection:

Tool (I): A structured interviewing questionnaire sheet. It included personal characteristics data of the study women such as (age, height, weight, body mass index "BMI" education level, occupation, residence, marital status).

Tool (II): The International Consultation on Incontinence Modular Questionnaire ICIQ-SF: The ICIQ is a self-reported survey and screening tool for evaluating the frequency, severity of urinary incontinence. The ICIQ-UI Short form provides a score ranging from 0-21; with a higher score indicating greater severity of symptoms; this assessment done before and after intervention.

Scoring system of the ICIQ-UI:

The total score is considered mild when <25% (<10points), Consider moderate when 25-50% (10-15 points), Consider sever when >50% (>15 points).

Procedure for Data Collection

Assessment phase

The researcher started to fill the interviewing questionnaire to assess women's personal characteristics, obstetric history, and urinary incontinence history.

Implementation phase:

The researcher provided the instructions to studied women about Kegel and breathing exercise through three months.

The researcher provided the instructions to women such as take deep breathing during the exercises; don't try to move legs, buttock, or abdominal muscles during the exercises, also the researcher instructed the studied women to relax for a period equal to the period of holding [11].

Evaluation phase:

The researcher evaluated effect of practicing deep breathing and Kegel exercises on stress urinary incontinence among elderly women as posttest by reassessing the frequency and severity of urinary incontinence and its effect on women's physical and psychological conditions by using the same tool of pretest and evaluate whether the frequency and severity and the effect of urinary incontinence decreased or not this tool took about 5-10 minutes.

Results

Table 1. Reveals that 49% of the studied sample aged 50-55 years old, and more than two-thirds (71%) were from rural areas; Also, more than half (51% & 52%) of them

were educated and working, respectively. Moreover, the majority (87%) was married and 52% of them were.

Table 2. Displays the distribution of studied sample according to body characteristics. It reveals that mean weight of the studied sample was 82.680 ± 11.8815 , mean height was 160.420 ± 2.8610 , and mean of BMI was 32.1224 ± 4.47973 .

Table 3. Indicates that there were highly statistically significant differences in the frequency of urine leakage of the studied sample after intervention than pre-intervention, also there were statistical differences in the amount of urine leaked per day.

Table 4. Reveals that there was negative correlation between age of the studied sample and their adherence to practicing deep breathing and Kegel exercises throughout the study.

Figure 1. Presents relationship between body mass index and frequency of urinary incontinence pre and post intervention. It reveals improvement of frequency of urinary incontinence for overweight and obese women. There was statistically significant association between BMI and frequency of urinary incontinence among the studied sample.

Table 1. Distribution of studied sample according to personal characteristics (n=100).

Personal Characteristics	%
Age (in years)	
50-55 years	49.0
> 55-60 years	38.0
>60 years	13.0
Residence	
Rural	71.0
Urban	29.0
Education	
Illiterate	49.0
Primary education	30.0
Secondary education	18.0
University education	3.0
Marital status	
Married	87.0
widower	13.0
Occupation	
House wife	48.0
Working	52.0

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of studied sample according to weight, height and Body Mass Index

	Minimum
Weight (Mean ±SD)	82.680±11.8815
Height (Mean ±SD)	160.420±2.8610
BMI (Mean ±SD)	32.1224±4.47973

Table 3. Distribution of studied sample according to their ICIQ-SF scale (n=100)

ICIQ-SF scale	Pre		Post		X ²	p-value
	No	%	No	%		
Frequency of urine leakage						
About once a week or less often	20	20.0	44	44.0	23.785	0.000**
Two or three times a week	30	30.0	24	24.0		
About once a day	5	5.0	13	13.0		
Several times a day	45	45.0	19	19.0		
The amount of urine leakage						
A small amount (under wear or pad is damp)	61	61.0	83	83.0	13.318	0.004*
A moderate amount (under wear or pad is wet)	32	32.0	12	12.0		
A large amount (under wear or pad is very wet)	7	7.0	5	5.0		
*Time of urine leakage						
Leaks before getting to the toilet	24	24.0	23	23.0	4.382	0.357
Leaks during cough or sneeze	10	10.0	10	10.0		
Leaks during sleeping	2	2.0	1	1.0		

*results not mutually exclusive

*significant at $p \leq 0.05$

**highly significant at $p \leq 0.01$

Table 4. Correlation between deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence and personal characteristics through the program phases (N=100)

Characteristics	deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence							
	1 st week of the 1 st month		At the end of the 1 st month		At the end of the 2 nd month		At the end of the 3 rd month	
	R	p-value	R	p-value	R	p-value	R	p-value
Age	-0.432	0.000	-0.675	0.000	-0.528	0.000	-0.409	0.000*
Education	0.460	0.000	0.437	0.000	0.237	0.018	0.279	0.005
Occupation	0.280	0.005	0.303	0.002	0.306	0.002	0.364	0.000
Residence	0.189	0.060	0.058	0.568	0.179	0.075	0.133	0.188
Marital status	0.208	0.038*	0.340	0.001	0.220	0.028*	0.339	0.001*

Person correlation coefficient test

*significant at $p \leq 0.05$

**highly significant at $p \leq 0.01$

Figure 1. Relationship between Body Mass Index and Frequency of Urinary Incontinence (Pre & Post Intervention)

Discussion

Stress urinary incontinence (SUI) affected menopausal women by reducing social and mental well-being such as loss of self-esteem, impaired body image, decreases the ability to maintain an independent life-style, social isolation, and clothing may become wet with urine which leads to embarrassment, and in particular, fear of unpleasant odor and sometimes sexual difficulties [11-12]. The current study aimed to evaluate effect of personal characteristics and body mass index on elderly women's urinary incontinence through the program phases.

Regarding correlation between Body Mass Index and the frequency of urinary incontinence, the current study demonstrated that there was statistical difference in the frequency of urinary incontinence in relation to Body Mass Index among the studied women after practicing deep breathing and kegel exercises. This was agreed with Jayachandran (2019) who assessed the Prevalence of Stress, Urge, and Mixed Urinary Incontinence in Women and mentioned that body mass index has been associated with urinary incontinence as the greatest number of women in the overweight and obese categories had stress urinary incontinence [13]. This result disagreed with Nygaard et al., (2019) who assessed the Impact of menopausal status on the outcome of pelvic floor physiotherapy in women with urinary incontinence and found no statistically significant association between BMI and frequency of urinary incontinence [14].

Regarding relationship between personal characteristics of the studied women and deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence the present study revealed that there was a positive significant correlation between education and working status of the studied

sample and their adherence to practicing deep breathing and Kegel exercises throughout the study.

Education for Upper Egyptian women had improved in recent decades. According to the present study findings, the most of the study subjects had a satisfactory level of education [15]. A positive significant correlation was found between deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence in related to women's education. It is not surprise to find that level of education has an effect on successes any program. As concerning to the level of education, the present study revealed that about half of the studied women were educated with different levels; this was similar to the results reported by Mohamed et al., (2021) who studied the Effect of Educational Interventions on Reducing Stress Urinary Incontinence Episodes among elderly Women and showed that near half almost of the studied women were in secondary and university education [16]. Also Mohamed et al (2018) who studied the effect of pelvic floor muscle strengthening-kegel's exercise on severity of stress urinary incontinence and quality of life among women and reported that two fifth of the control and slightly more than fifth of the study groups had primary and secondary education [17].

In contrast to the current study, Wang & Ying (2019) who studied the Effect of pelvic floor muscle training on the pelvic floor muscle and tonus & Altman et al., (2019) who studied the Epidemiology of urinary incontinence and other lower urinary tract symptoms pelvic organ prolapse and anal incontinence both of them stated that most of the studied women was illiterate women and there was a significant relation between the prevalence of stress urinary incontinence and illiterate women ,this rational why women with (SUI) don't think that they are need in medical advice [18-19].

Regarding the working, the present study showed that slightly more than half of the studied women were working, this come in agreement with Ismail et al (2019) who studied the Effect of Kegel Exercise on Severity of Urinary Incontinence and Quality of Life among Menopausal Women and mentioned that More than one-half of both groups were working [20]. However, this was disagreed with Taha (2020) who studied the prevalence of stress urinary incontinence of females' child-bearing period at Shubra-Bass Village, Menoufiya Governorate and reported that approximately near half of the studied women were house wives and stated that there was a significant relation between the prevalence of (SUI) and unemployed female among Menoufiya women [21]. A significant positive correlation was found between deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence in related to women's occupation. This is attributed to that the employed had the highest empowerment when compared with the unemployed ones. Work ensures the independence and financial security and provides sources for seeking health care [15].

concerning to the place of residence, the present study clarified that slightly more than two thirds of the studied women were from rural areas and this was in the same line with Taha (2020) who studied the prevalence of stress urinary incontinence of females' child-bearing period at Shubra-Bass Village, Menoufiya Governorate and Mohamed et al., (2021) who studied the Effect of Educational Interventions on

Reducing Stress Urinary Incontinence Episodes among elderly Women and Ng et al., (2020) who studied the Risk factors and prevalence of urinary incontinence in mid-life Singaporean women all of them pointed that highest percentage of stress urinary incontinence among women especially those from a rural area [21,16, 17]. This result may due to that women from rural area might be working in the farm, and carry heavy object, and delivered more children because culture in rural area encourages increased number of children. In contrast Mohamed et al (2018) who studied the Effect of pelvic floor muscle strengthening-kegel exercise on severity of stress urinary incontinence and quality of life among women and found that the majority of the studied group and nearly half of control group were from urban area [18].

Residence surly affect many variables; rural dwellers marry in very young age which in turn effects on general condition of women and expose them to many health problems. This might be ascribable to the fact that day by day life enhances women's experience and decline their knowledge. Early marriage could have a negative effect on the women's education; this had exposed these women not only to ignorance of their condition but also to complications. Early marriage has hindered women to complete their education and to get an appropriate job and had become financially dependent on their kin. Therefore, teen women were more likely to live in poverty than women who were in delayed marriage age. Moreover, delaying age at marriage was a key to improving women's status and may be a way of increasing their leverages in the decision-making process [15].

Conclusion

Remarkable improvement in urinary incontinence according to ICIQ-SF scale is observed after practice of deep breathing and Kegel exercise. Deep breathing and kegel exercises adherence is affected by personal characteristics and body mass index for the elderly women through the intervention phases. Hypotheses were accepted

Recommendations

Developing awareness program regarding importance and benefits of practicing deep breathing and kegel exercises to reduce stress urinary incontinence symptoms among elderly women.

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